

STORING GRAPES AT HOME

Saydullayeva Madina

The third year student of Tashkent State Agricultural University

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Abstract. Any summer resident knows that juicy and tender berries are practically not stored: they must either be eaten immediately, or twisted for the winter, or frozen. But grapes are an exception. There are ways that allow you to store grapes at home all winter. Only here it is important to remember: early grapes are not suitable for storage. Only mid-season and late varieties are capable of lying for a long time. But also not all - the ability to be well stored is indicated in the characteristics of the variety. Therefore, before buying seedlings, if you want to enjoy berries all winter, carefully read the annotation.

Key words: storage of grapes, grape varieties, drying of grapes, placement of grapes.

ХРАНЕНИЕ ВИНОГРАДА ДОМА

Аннотация. Любой дачник знает, что сочные и нежные ягоды практически не хранятся: их нужно либо сразу есть, либо закручивать на зиму, либо замораживать. Но виноград является исключением. Есть способы, позволяющие хранить виноград в домашних условиях всю зиму. Только вот важно помнить: ранний виноград для хранения не годится. Только среднеспелые и поздние сорта способны долго лежать. Но тоже не все – способность хорошо храниться указана в характеристиках сорта. Поэтому перед покупкой саженцев, если вы хотите всю зиму лакомиться ягодами, внимательно прочитайте аннотацию.

Ключевые слова: хранение винограда, сорта винограда, сушка винограда, размещение винограда.

INTRODUCTION

Any summer resident knows that juicy and tender berries are practically not stored: they must either be eaten immediately, or twisted for the winter, or frozen. But grapes are an exception. There are ways that allow you to store grapes at home all winter.

Only here it is important to remember: early grapes are not suitable for storage. Only mid-season and late varieties are capable of lying for a long time. But also not all - the ability to be well stored is indicated in the characteristics of the variety.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

But that's not all. In order for the grapes to lie without problems until spring, at the end of the season it is necessary to provide the grapes with special agricultural technology.

Leaving at the end of the season

Harvest regulation. The first thing to do in early autumn is to remove a third of the crop from the plant. This is necessary so that the remaining bunches receive more nutrition and ripen better.

Watering. They are now contraindicated - they must be stopped at the end of July. Otherwise, the berries will be watery, and these are not stored for a long time.

Top dressing. The next step is fertilization. In early September, the grapes must be fed with phosphorus and potassium: 1 tbsp. a spoonful of superphosphate and potassium sulfate per 10 liters of water. Consumption rate - a bucket for 1 plant. Proponents of organic farming can

replace mineral fertilizers with ash - 1 cup should be evenly distributed in the root zone and watered.

Of course, nitrogen fertilization is excluded at this time - they can provoke the growth of the vine to the detriment of the crop. And the berries after nitrogen fertilizing at the end of the season will not be stored.

Harvest

Clusters intended for storage should be harvested only after they are fully ripe - berries do not ripen outside the bush. But it also makes no sense to delay harvesting - overripe grapes lie very badly. In addition, there is a high probability that the berries will beat the frost.

RESULTS

It is necessary to harvest the crop in dry weather. During rains, a lot of moisture accumulates in the berries and the amount of sugar decreases, and the less it is, the worse the clusters are stored.

You need to cut the clusters with secateurs and very carefully - it is important not to wipe the wax coating from the berries, because it is he who protects the crop from spoilage.

And there are a few more points that affect the storage of grapes:

- bunches ripened on the south side of the vine are better stored;
- berries collected from old bushes lie longer;
- berries ripened in a dry summer are stored less;
- berries with a lot of sugar lie longer - it should be at least 18%.

Ways to store grapes

There are different options for storing grapes at home, but in any case, he needs to provide 3 main conditions:

- temperature - 0...+2 °C;
- humidity - 85 - 90%;
- complete darkness.
- Such conditions can be provided in the cellar.

In boxes. For storing grapes, wooden boxes with slots between the planks are ideal - they are needed so that the berries are ventilated. At the bottom of the box, you need to pour sawdust of deciduous trees (coniferous trees are not suitable - the grapes will smell of resin) or lay out straw.

Bunches should be laid in one layer with ridges up. And it is also important that they do not touch each other.

In water. In this case, the clusters must be cut with a piece of vine so that one internode remains above the cluster, and two under it. The upper cut must be covered with plasticine or filled with paraffin. And put the bottom one in a 1.5-liter bottle of water. Just do not make bouquets of grapes - there should be only one branch in each bottle.

So that the water does not go dry, you need to add a pinch of salt and a crumb of charcoal to it. And so that it does not evaporate, the neck must be plugged with cotton wool. The water needs to be changed every 2 weeks.

In the ashes this is the easiest way: you just need to dust the bunches with ashes and put them in the cellar - you can simply lay them out on the shelves. But even here there is a little trick - not any ash is suitable, but only straw.

But it is important to take into account one point - you need to cut not just bunches, but with part of the vine - so they will sag for six months longer! Because part of the vine during storage will give sugar to the berries, and the more sugar they contain, the longer they do not deteriorate.

Rooted. This method is quite troublesome, but the most reliable. Now, of course, it's too late to use it, but take note for next year.

Its essence is this: in early July, when the berries are the size of a pea, under the clusters that are supposed to be sent for storage, you need to cut off all the leaves and put a bottle on the vine. First, you need to cut off the neck along the “shoulders”, make a cut in the side for the entire length and to the middle of the bottom, and in the bottom - a hole along the diameter of the shoot. After the bottle is put on, the slot must be sealed with adhesive tape and loose earth is poured into it.

DISCUSSION

During the summer, the soil in the bottle must be watered so that it is always slightly moist. Over the summer, roots form on the part of the shoot that was in the bottle. When the berries are ripe, the shoot must be cut off - from the bottom flush with the bottom of the bottle, and on top leave one internode above the bunch.

CONCLUSIONS

That is, in the end you will get a kind of grape seedling with berries. It must be removed to the basement and watered as the soil dries. In this form, grapes can be stored until the end of spring.

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